

Clinical Case: Anesthetic Management for Maxillectomy Due to Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma

Josue Alberto Ramirez Burgos*¹, Ghyna Mineli Herrera Aguilar²

¹Third-year anesthesiology resident physician. Regional High Specialty Hospital of the Yucatan Peninsula. Faculty of Medicine, Autonomous University of Yucatan.

²Anesthesiologist assigned to the anesthesiology service. Regional High Specialty Hospital of the Yucatan Peninsula.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Anesthetic management in oncologic maxillectomy represents a major challenge due to airway complexity, risk of hemorrhage, and anatomical alterations secondary to tumor progression and prior treatments such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Adenoid cystic carcinoma is a rare neoplasm characterized by aggressive local invasion and high recurrence rates. **Case Presentation:** A 59-year-old male with locally advanced adenoid cystic carcinoma of the left hemiface presented with a large facial tumor ($\approx 11 \times 9 \times 8$ cm) causing anatomical distortion and predictors of difficult airway (Mallampati III, limited oral opening). Despite prior chemotherapy and radiotherapy, disease progression required suprastructural maxillectomy with orbital exenteration and flap reconstruction. Anesthetic management included intravenous induction, successful orotracheal intubation on first attempt via direct laryngoscopy, and maintenance with inhalational anesthesia, opioids, and dexmedetomidine. Intraoperatively, significant blood loss (≈ 1200 ml) required transfusion and vasopressor support. Electrolyte disturbances and a cutaneous reaction were managed without major complications. The patient was extubated awake after airway reassessment and had an uneventful postoperative course with adequate pain control and no respiratory compromise. **Clinical Findings and Outcomes:** The case highlights successful airway management despite multiple predictors of difficulty, effective control of hemorrhage with goal-directed strategies, and favorable postoperative recovery without major complications. **Discussion:** Maxillectomy in head and neck cancer requires a comprehensive anesthetic approach addressing airway management, hemodynamic stability, bleeding control, and postoperative care. Prior radiotherapy and chemotherapy significantly increase airway difficulty and perioperative risks. Multimodal analgesia and careful fluid management are essential to optimize outcomes and reduce complications. **Conclusion:** An individualized, multidisciplinary anesthetic strategy is essential in complex oncologic maxillectomy. Careful preoperative planning, anticipation of complications, and application of multimodal perioperative management can achieve favorable outcomes even in high-risk patients.

KEYWORDS: Anesthesia; maxillectomy; adenoid cystic carcinoma; difficult airway; head and neck cancer

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INTRODUCTION

Surgical interventions for the treatment of maxillofacial tumors represent a multidisciplinary challenge involving anesthesiologists, surgeons, and other specialties. Anesthetic management, including perioperative airway management, is particularly challenging in patients with head and neck

cancer. Primary lesions of the airway structures not only tend to obstruct them but are also associated with a risk of bleeding during manipulation. Other factors that complicate airway management during oral cancer surgery include sharing the airway with the surgical team, prolonged surgical duration, the presence of trismus, and decreased submental mobility

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due to prior radiotherapy. Airways may be further compromised intraoperatively due to surgical manipulation causing laryngopharyngeal edema and bulky flaps invading the oral cavity, reducing airway caliber. All these factors can make re-securing the airway after extubation extremely difficult. Therefore, airway management in maxillofacial cancer surgery presents unique challenges not only during surgery but also in the postoperative period. Additionally, oncologic treatments such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy, the cancer itself, malnutrition, and associated comorbidities can adversely affect the patient's general condition and must be considered during evaluation. Patients undergoing these procedures require an individualized and careful anesthetic approach. [I] Adenoid cystic carcinoma is an uncommon tumor of the head and neck, typically located in salivary glands, although cutaneous involvement has also been described.

Metastases are rare, but recurrence occurs in approximately 50% of cases. Anesthetic considerations for its resection are critical due to airway complexity and proximity to vital structures. Careful preoperative planning is essential for airway management in patients with head and neck cancer undergoing general anesthesia. This includes a detailed physical examination, comprehensive medical history, and close communication between the surgeon and anesthesiologist. It is crucial to ensure that all necessary airway equipment is available before induction of anesthesia. In situations where advanced technologies are unavailable (such as videolaryngoscopes or fiberoptic bronchoscopes), and in cases of severe trismus, awake tracheostomy may be more appropriate. [II] In such cases, adequate local anesthesia and effective communication between surgeon and patient are essential to ensure cooperation and a controlled procedure.

These considerations are especially relevant in resource-limited regions, where access to advanced technologies may be restricted, highlighting the importance of planning and communication in anesthetic management.

Maxillectomy is a complex surgical procedure involving partial or total resection of the maxilla. It is commonly performed to treat malignant or aggressive tumors, severe trauma, and advanced osteonecrosis. Anesthesia in these cases presents multiple challenges due to proximity to critical structures, risk of severe bleeding, and airway management difficulties. [III] Maxillectomies may be classified as medial (removal of part of the maxilla near the nose while preserving the eye and hard palate), infrastructural (removal of part of the hard palate and maxilla while preserving the orbital floor), or suprastructural (removal of the orbital floor along with the upper maxilla while preserving the remaining hard palate). In extensive disease, total maxillectomy or total palatotomy may be required to ensure clear margins, involving removal of the hard palate, orbital floor, and maxilla on one or both sides. These procedures require reconstruction using flaps to prevent globe sinking and to restore masticatory, swallowing, and anatomical function. [I]

Specific guidelines for preanesthetic evaluation in patients with adenoid cystic tumors are not exclusively detailed in the literature. However, general recommendations, such as those provided by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA), are applicable and relevant. [IV]

Furthermore, with ERAS (Enhanced Recovery After Surgery) protocols available for head and neck surgery, increasing evidence suggests that outcomes can significantly improve with standardized perioperative care. These protocols emphasize goal-directed therapy, nutrition, postoperative analgesia, and perioperative rehabilitation, with the anesthesiologist playing a key role. A future goal is to expand ERAS adoption in head and neck cancer surgeries. [V]

CASE REPORT

59-year-old male, Mexican nationality, merchant, weight 78.2 kg, height 1.63 m, BMI 29.43. Condition began 8 years ago with the presence of a pigmented lesion (mole) in the left infraorbital region after trauma with steel material, presenting bleeding and inflammation, with partial improvement. Two years ago, there was an increase in volume progressing to limitation of palpebral opening; he was referred to this unit in September 2022, biopsy was indicated and performed in October 2022 with Histopathological Report (HPR) for adenoid cystic carcinoma; however, the patient was lost to follow-up for 5 months. Patient evaluated for neoadjuvant Chemotherapy (CT) and Radiotherapy (RT), starting 8 cycles of neoadjuvant CT and 30 sessions of RT, with poor response to treatment. He was protocolized for preoperative evaluations, MRI, and surgical management.

Non-pathological history: cocaine use since age 35, discontinued 10 years ago; alcohol use without reaching intoxication; other drug use denied. Facial trauma with nasal fracture 20 years ago, conservatively managed; fractures of 5th and 4th fingers of right hand, not requiring surgical treatment. Allergy to sulfonamides. Surgical: 14.10.2022 Tru-cut biopsy lesion, HPR malignant neoplasm compatible with adenoid cystic carcinoma; 22.04.2024 diagnostic angiography + chemoembolization of left internal maxillary artery and left facial artery. Pathological history of locally advanced adenoid cystic carcinoma, under medical treatment with neoadjuvant CT 8 sessions carboplatin 200 mg + gemcitabine 300 mg + paclitaxel (last in October 2023), RT 30 sessions (last September 2023).

On physical examination patient is oriented in all three spheres, freely chosen posture, adequate coloration of skin and mucosa, regular hydration status, normocephalic skull, tumor observed over left zygomatic and maxillary region, approximately 11x9x8 cm, stony consistency, fixed to planes, causing closure of palpebral opening and presence of ulceration of ipsilateral conjunctival mucosa, globe not visualized. Left narina displaced by tumor, mouth and palate without alterations; short, cylindrical, symmetrical neck with centrally located, mobile trachea; thorax with adequate

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expansion and excursion; rest of examination without apparent alterations.

Oral opening class II (3 cm), Mallampati III, Patil-Aldrete class I (7 cm), sternomental distance I (13 cm), Bellhouse-Dor[√] Grade II, mandibular protrusion class II, El-Ganzouri <4, neck circumference 42 cm, edentulous due to lower molars, mobile incisors, no prosthesis use, regular hygiene status.

Preoperative evaluation by internal medicine 11.12.2023 Goldman I, intermediate Lee, no recommendations issued. Ophthalmology 30.06.2023: poor visual prognosis for left eye. Preanesthetic evaluation 14.12.2023 ASA III, RAQ E3B, moderate airway risk, intermediate respiratory risk, functional capacity >4 METS.

Imaging studies: CT 12.04.2023 tumor in left hemiface 76x67 mm, expansive, with bony erosion of maxillary bones, nasolacrimal canal and ipsilateral orbit. Brain MRI 18.01.2024 bilateral frontoparietal microangiopathic leukoencephalopathy / leukoaraiosis. Facial MRI 18.01.2024 at left inferior periorbital region irregular, lobulated, well-defined, heterogeneous lesion, predominantly T2 hyperintense, measuring 9.3 x 6.6 x 8.7 cm, with extraconal extension as well as to ethmoidal cells and ipsilateral frontal sinus, with contrast enhancement.

Laboratories 22.04.2024: Hb 13.6, Hct 38.10, leukocytes 6.96, platelets 191, Na 141, K 3.6, Cl 107.7, Ca 6.9, P 3.4, Mg 1.7, PT 11.5, Act 105, INR 1.07, aPTT 28.2, glucose 85.8, urea 27.5, creatinine 0.83, uric acid 4.7, TB 0.37, DB 0.20, IB 0.17, total proteins 6.5, albumin 4.4, globulin 2.1, A/G ratio 2.1, AST 16, ALT 18, ALP 61, GGT 71.

Surgery performed 25.04.2024: en bloc resection (suprastructural maxillectomy), orbital exenteration, flap rotation. Procedure performed by oncologic surgery, maxillofacial surgery and plastic reconstructive surgery. (Figure 1 and 2)

POST-ANESTHETIC NOTE: On arrival hemodynamically stable, BP 115/73 mmHg, HR 74, RR 16, SpO2 99%, airway Mallampati (M) III, Oral Opening (OO) I, Patil-Aldrete (PA) II, Sternomental Distance (SMD) II, Bellhouse-Dor[√] (BHD) I, conscious, oriented, GCS 15 points, rhythmic precordium without added sounds, lung fields without pleuropulmonary syndromes, tumor in left maxilla with deviation of nasal septum to the right, anesthetic technique and risks explained, anesthetic consent signed. RAQ E3B, high airway risk, reserved prognosis according to evolution.

After checking anesthesia machine and resuscitation equipment, patient enters OR, non-invasive monitoring placed, BP 140/81 mmHg, HR 61, RR 16, SpO2 100%, preoxygenation started with O2 at 5 L/min, induction fentanyl 300 mcg IV, lidocaine 80 mg IV, rocuronium 50 mg IV, propofol 100 mg IV, mask ventilation HAN II, pharmacological latency, direct laryngoscopy MAC 3, Cormack Lehane II, orotracheal intubation on first attempt ETT 8.0, cuff 4 cc, position confirmed with capnography,

capnometry and auscultation, secured at 22 cm. During the procedure ETT fixed at 22 cm to gingiva with silk suture. Volume-controlled mechanical ventilation maintained with VT 460 cc, RR 14/min, FiO2 60%, PEEP 5, I:E 1:2. Second peripheral catheter No. 14 placed. Then triple lumen central venous catheter placed in right jugular vein, ultrasound-guided with Seldinger technique, first attempt. Right radial arterial line placed with No. 20 catheter, aseptic technique, without complications.

Maintenance: Sevoflurane 0.8-0.9 MAC, fentanyl infusion 0.052 mcg/kg/min (total final dose 1450 mcg IV), dexmedetomidine infusion total dose 156 mcg. Adjuncts: dexamethasone 8 mg IV, paracetamol 1 g IV, metronidazole 1 g IV, ceftazidime 1 g IV, ketorolac 60 mg IV, ondansetron 8 mg IV, calcium gluconate 1 g IV. Tranexamic acid 1 g IV. Hemodynamics: bleeding 600 cc, first PRBC requested, norepinephrine started at 0.13 mcg/kg/min maintaining MAP 77 mmHg. Final bleeding 1200 cc, urine output 2290 cc, Hartmann solution 4200 cc, normal saline 3000 cc. Blood products: 2 PRBC, 1 FFP transfused during procedure.

Arterial blood gas follow-up:

pH 7.46, pCO2 33, pO2 247, Na+ 141, K+ 3.0, Ca++ 0.89, Glucose 86, Lactate 0.6, Hb 10.5, HCO3- 23.8, BE -0.1

pH 7.41, pCO2 34, pO2 272, Na+ 136, K+ 3.2, Ca++ 1.01, Glucose 145, Lactate 1.0, Hb 9.9, HCO3- 21.8, BE -2.8

pH 7.37, pCO2 31, pO2 248, Na+ 140, K+ 2.7, Ca++ 0.79, Glucose 176, Lactate 2.7, Hb 5.9, HCO3- 18.3, BE -6.9

pH 7.32, pCO2 36, pO2 227, Na+ 137, K+ 3.5, Ca++ 0.95, Glucose 241, Lactate 3.8, Hb 10.9, HCO3- 18.7, BE -7.1

Intraoperatively patient developed generalized rash, hydrocortisone 200 mg IV and diphenhydramine 50 mg IV administered. Direct laryngoscopy performed without visualization of vocal cord edema or airway compromise.

Gentle suctioning of secretions, spontaneous recovery, protective airway reflexes present, patient extubated awake without complications. Discharge vitals BP 128/75 mmHg, HR 70, RR 16, SpO2 100%. Anesthesia time 8 h 45 min, ALDRETE 9, VAS 4, Ramsay 3. Plan: transfer to PACU, continuous cardiac monitoring, monitor for respiratory distress, supplemental O2 via reservoir mask at 6 L/min. During PACU stay patient without respiratory distress, hemodynamically stable, no vasopressors required, pain VAS 4, ALDRETE 10, discharged to oncologic surgery ward.

FOLLOW-UP: Histopathological report 15.05.2024 adenoid cystic carcinoma with cribriform pattern with extensive necrosis measuring 9x7x7 cm invading eyelid skin and destroying maxillary bone. Surgical margins superior and inferior negative for neoplasm. Surgical bed with macroscopic neoplasm, immunohistochemistry requested.

During follow-up in oncologic surgery outpatient clinic, patient with adequate oral intake tolerance, no significant dysphagia, no chronic pain; surgical treatment considered definitive, continuing follow-up in oncology and oncologic surgery clinic.

Figure 1. Intraoperative view of the maxillary region showing extensive tumor involvement and surgical resection field during maxillectomy procedure.

Figure 2. Left: Intraoperative image demonstrating extensive maxillary tumor resection with exposure of underlying structures. Right: Postoperative appearance following reconstructive surgery with flap placement and surgical closure.

DISCUSSION

The anesthetic approach to oncologic maxillectomy must be analyzed from a comprehensive perspective that includes the preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative phases, as each presents specific challenges and determines the overall patient outcome.

In the preoperative phase, thorough evaluation of the airway and associated comorbidities is critical, particularly in patients with a history of radiotherapy or chemotherapy that predispose to fibrosis, trismus, and tissue fragility. Likewise, optimization of nutritional, hematologic, and metabolic status represents a cornerstone to reduce perioperative complications, although it is often limited by the advanced stage of the disease. Early communication with the surgical team and planning of difficult airway strategies and transfusion management are essential parts of this preparation.

During the intraoperative phase, the main challenges include securing a shared airway, controlling potentially massive hemorrhage, maintaining hemodynamic stability during prolonged surgeries, and preventing complications derived from fluid therapy and analgesia. The use of multimodal techniques, selection of balanced solutions, and anticipation of metabolic complications (hypocalcemia, acidosis, electrolyte disorders) are measures that directly impact anesthetic safety.

Finally, in the postoperative phase, close monitoring of the airway—with high risk of edema, bleeding, or collapse—and early detection of respiratory or hemodynamic complications are priorities. In addition, aspects such as pain control with multimodal regimens, infection prevention, monitoring of reconstructive flaps, and early functional rehabilitation form the basis for safe and effective recovery.

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This phase-based analysis allows contextualization of the case findings and comparison with current evidence, highlighting both appropriate decisions and areas for improvement that may guide future clinical practice in anesthetic management of highly complex oncologic surgeries.

Airway: predictors, securing strategy, and extubation

The present case concentrated multiple predictors of difficult airway: large facial tumor ($\approx 11 \times 9 \times 8$ cm) with anatomical distortion, oral opening 3 cm (Mallampati III), possible impact of prior radiotherapy on soft tissues, and risk of bleeding during manipulation. These elements increase the probability of difficult ventilation and intubation and of post-resection compromise due to edema/structural changes; additionally, the airway is shared with the surgical team, with risk of tube displacement, need for tracheostomy, or delayed extubation depending on the intraoperative scenario. In this case, despite predictors, orotracheal intubation with direct laryngoscopy (Cormack–Lehane II) was successful on the first attempt, with verification by capnography and secure fixation, underscoring the importance of methodical preoxygenation, planned induction, and availability of alternative plans (videolaryngoscopy/fiberoptic bronchoscope and surgical access) when difficulty is anticipated. [X]

In patients with head and neck cancer, evidence supports structured preoperative planning (history and airway-focused examination, imaging review, close coordination with surgery) and availability of advanced equipment and rescue plans, considering awake intubation when airway collapse is a tangible risk under general anesthesia. Awake tracheostomy remains a valid alternative in contexts of severe trismus, major distortion, or limited resources, always with adequate local anesthesia and informed consent. [X]

Regarding extubation, extensive maxillectomy and flap procedures are associated with laryngopharyngeal edema, bleeding risk, and anatomical remodeling; in this context, extubation is high-risk and must be strategic. Two reasonable approaches are:

- Delayed extubation (8–12 h) in ICU when there are bulky flaps, prior radiotherapy, extensive resection, or bilateral cervical exploration. [XV–XVI]
- Extubation in the operating room with prior endoscopic/laryngoscopic evaluation, full reversal of neuromuscular blockade, and tube exchanger in situ for up to 4 h to facilitate reintubation if necessary. [XV–XVI]

In this case, immediate extubation was achieved without complications, but—given the prolonged surgery and significant bleeding—a delayed extubation strategy would have also been justifiable if final examination had shown significant edema or if the team anticipated difficult reintubation. [XVIII] The key is to individualize the decision according to resection extent, post-radiation tissue status, and institutional logistics (availability of equipment and expert

personnel) with an explicit rescue plan (fiberoptic bronchoscope, videolaryngoscope, and surgical access).

Hemorrhage and hemodynamics in maxillectomy

Intraoperative hemorrhage constitutes one of the most relevant complications in extensive head and neck surgeries such as maxillectomy, due to the abundant vascularization of the maxillofacial region and proximity to major structures (maxillary artery, facial branches, pterygoid venous plexus). In this case, significant blood loss was recorded requiring replacement with blood products and crystalloid solutions, consistent with literature reports where bleeding ranges from 500 ml to more than 2 L depending on tumor extent and surgical technique. [VI]

Hemodynamic management focused on maintaining adequate mean arterial pressure (MAP) to ensure cerebral and tissue perfusion, avoiding prolonged hypotension that could compromise the surgical flap or systemic oxygenation. Guidelines recommend controlled hypotension strategies only selectively and in patients without severe cardiovascular comorbidities, as although they reduce blood loss, they may increase the risk of ischemia in vital organs.

In these procedures, the use of tranexamic acid is considered an effective measure to reduce bleeding and transfusion requirements. Various studies in head and neck oncologic surgery demonstrate decreased intraoperative hemorrhage without a clear increase in thrombotic complications, making its inclusion in protocols advisable.

Transfusion management should be goal-directed: hemoglobin >7 – 8 g/dl in stable patients, with higher thresholds in elderly or those with cardiovascular disease. Replacement of ionized calcium during massive transfusion is essential, as citrate-induced hypocalcemia from blood products can cause arrhythmias and myocardial depression. In this case, reductions in potassium and serum calcium were documented, consistent with this pathophysiology and highlighting the need for close real-time monitoring of electrolytes and arterial blood gases.

Current evidence favors the application of goal-directed hemodynamic therapy, using parameters such as cardiac index, stroke volume variation, and central venous saturation, rather than relying solely on blood pressure or cumulative fluid balance. This approach has shown reduction in postoperative complications, hospital stay, and risk of fluid overload, particularly critical in head and neck surgery due to airway edema risk. [XII]

Hemorrhage in maxillectomy must be addressed with a comprehensive plan:

- Anticipation of bleeding with preoperative crossmatching of blood products.
- Consider tranexamic acid from induction.
- Advanced hemodynamic monitoring when available.
- Individualized transfusion strategy with electrolyte correction.

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- Prevention of fluid overload that increases airway edema risk.

Fluids: goal-directed therapy and airway edema

Fluid management in head and neck oncologic surgery represents a particular challenge, as adequate tissue perfusion and hemodynamic stability must be maintained without causing overload that may promote upper airway edema. This risk is especially relevant in prolonged procedures such as maxillectomy, where tissue manipulation, extensive resection, and long surgical time increase local inflammation and post-extubation obstruction potential. [XII]

The traditional practice of liberal crystalloid administration has been questioned, as it is associated with increased respiratory complications, anastomotic leakage, and prolonged hospital stay. In contrast, restrictive or balanced fluid strategies guided by dynamic parameters and Goal-Directed Therapy (GDT) principles have shown better postoperative outcomes and lower edema incidence. These include the use of advanced monitoring (e.g., stroke volume variation, cardiac output, central venous saturation) to individualize fluid and vasopressor administration. [XII]

In this case, replacement was performed with balanced crystalloids and blood products, with clinical monitoring of perfusion and mean arterial pressure. However, the lack of advanced hemodynamic monitoring limited full implementation of a goal-directed fluid protocol. This scenario reflects the reality of many centers where decisions rely mainly on anesthesiologist experience and conventional parameters (heart rate, blood pressure, urine output), increasing clinical variability.

Evidence suggests that balanced solutions compared to chloride-rich solutions (such as 0.9% saline) reduce the risk of hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis and acute kidney injury, complications that directly impact recovery. Likewise, in patients at risk of postoperative laryngeal edema, excess crystalloid administration is associated with increased need for prolonged ventilation and risk of reintubation. [XII]

Optimal fluid management in maxillectomy should consider:

- Avoid fluid overload that promotes edema and respiratory complications.
- Prefer balanced solutions over 0.9% sodium chloride.
- Incorporate, when possible, goal-directed therapy with dynamic monitoring.
- Maintain neutral or slightly negative balance at the end of surgery without compromising tissue perfusion.

Multimodal analgesia and role of dexmedetomidine/opioids

Pain control in head and neck surgery, particularly oncologic maxillectomies, is a critical aspect of postoperative recovery, as inadequate analgesia is associated with increased stress response, delayed functional rehabilitation, and risk of respiratory complications due to hypoventilation or ineffective cough.

Modern strategies rely on multimodal analgesia, combining different drugs and techniques to enhance efficacy and reduce opioid dependence. In this case, analgesia was based on intraoperative opioids complemented with NSAIDs and paracetamol, allowing hemodynamic stability and adequate anesthetic depth. However, procedure complexity highlights the need to integrate additional agents and techniques to optimize outcomes.

Dexmedetomidine, an α_2 -adrenergic agonist, has shown benefits: reduces opioid consumption, provides cooperative sedation, and has a favorable airway profile without significant respiratory depression. Additionally, it helps control sympathetic response to pain and bleeding. Limitations include bradycardia and hypotension, requiring careful titration and close monitoring. [XIII-XIV]

Regarding opioids, although they remain a cornerstone, their use must be cautious due to adverse effects such as respiratory depression, nausea, vomiting, and delayed recovery. In head and neck surgery patients, postoperative respiratory depression is particularly dangerous due to airway edema or anatomical changes. Therefore, reduced doses, short-acting opioids, and non-opioid adjuncts are recommended. [XX-XXI]

Regional blocks (infraorbital, maxillary, superficial cervical) have shown usefulness in multimodal analgesia, reducing opioid requirements and improving comfort, although their use may be limited by tumor extent or surgical resection.

In conclusion, the safest and most effective approach is an individualized multimodal scheme combining:

- Non-opioid analgesics (paracetamol, NSAIDs) from preoperative phase.
- Reduced-dose opioids, preferably short-acting.
- Consider dexmedetomidine as adjunct.
- Locoregional techniques when feasible.

Impact of radiotherapy/chemotherapy on airway and oral complications

In patients undergoing head and neck oncologic surgery, prior RT and CT cause anatomical and functional changes that must be prioritized in anesthetic planning. [VII-IX] Radiotherapy causes fibrosis, reduced elasticity, trismus, chronic edema, and mucosal fragility, complicating intubation and healing, and increasing necrosis risk. Chemotherapy may induce mucositis, xerostomia, hematologic alterations, and immunosuppression, increasing infection and bleeding risk. These factors also increase risk of aspiration and respiratory compromise after extubation, making multidisciplinary evaluation essential.

Comparison with literature

Findings are consistent with literature regarding difficult airway, bleeding risk, and complications. Radiotherapy increases airway difficulty and healing issues; chemotherapy increases infection and bleeding risk. Preparation and individualized planning align with current recommendations.

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Protocols ERAS in head and neck

ERAS protocols aim to improve recovery and reduce complications. Partial implementation was achieved in this case (analgesia, antibiotics, monitoring), but limitations existed in nutrition, advanced monitoring, and rehabilitation.

CONCLUSION

Patients with maxillofacial cancer represent a challenge for anesthesiologists. Thorough evaluation and meticulous planning are required. Airway management is a major challenge for both intubation and safe extubation. Other aspects such as bleeding, hemodynamic control, and multimodal pain management are equally important. Oncologic patients present significant risk factors (effects of chemotherapy, radiotherapy, malnutrition, pain). An individualized, multidisciplinary perioperative approach is required to achieve optimal outcomes and facilitate early return to daily activities.

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Conflicts of Interest: None.

Ethical Considerations: The patient was informed at all times about the diagnosis, interventions performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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